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A STUDY ON COLOR SCHEME IN CHINESE COMMERCIAL INTERIOR SPACE

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ABSTRACT

The harmony of color in the commercial interior space is affected by local culture and color scheme¹⁾. The objective of this research is to investigate the characteristics of color scheme in Chinese Commercial interior Space.

A field survey was done in 8 major cities in China. CIE Lab values of wall, roof, floor and sign of each sample were measured.

Results shows that color scheme in commercial space have distinctions in different areas in China. Color distribution of south and central area is vivid hue, high saturation and high brightness. Color distribution of north, east and west areas is warm hue, lower saturation and lower brightness. The brightness in supermarket is darker than other spaces, and the sign colors used in these spaces are quiet different with each other. Departments are brighter than others, supermarkets are darker than others.

Keywords: Color Scheme, Local Culture, Commercial Space

1. INTRODUCTION

The harmony of color in the commercial interior space is affected by local culture and color scheme. China is developing rapidly now, especially in building trade. More international communications are needed in architecture design area, but Chinese preference for color scheme in interior space is seldom studied, and in lots of cases, international design communications couldn't go on smoothly in China. Therefore, Chinese local color scheme should be investigated to make international design communication go on more smoothly. The objective of this research is to investigate the characteristics

of color scheme in Chinese Commercial interior Space.

2. METHOD

2.1 SAMPLES

A field survey was done in 8 major cities in China, including 2 north cities, 3 east cities, 1 central city, 1 south city and 1 west city. 240 samples were collected. CIE Lab values of each sample were measured by color spectrometer and color guide, including wall color, roof color, floor color and sign color. Wall color includes wall' color and column's color, sign color include background color, font color and frame color, floor color including more than 2 colors when use the colorful materials.

	Area	City	Samples
1	North	Beijing	48
2		Qingdao	28
3	East	Shanghai	48
4		Hangzhou	23
5		Suzhou	15
6	Central	Wuhan	24
7	South	Guangzhou	26
8	West	Chongqing	28

2.2 CHINESE COMMERCIAL SPACES

In this research, samples were taken in 3 major kinds of Chinese commercial Spaces, including department stores where is designed for Chinese consumers with high consumption, shopping malls where is designed for consumers with general consumptions or recreational consumptions, and markets or supermarkets where is designed for consumers with general or lower consumptions.

We changed the CIE Lab values into HSB values to confirm the values of Hue, Saturation and Brightness.

2.3 ANALYSES

CIE Lab values were changed to HSB values to confirm the values of hue, Saturation and Brightness of each sample. The color distributions of samples in different areas, color distribution in different type of commercial space were analyzed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 COLOR DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT AREAS

Color distribution of different areas is shown in graph 1 and graph 2. Hue value of floor is concentrated on 0-60, and west of China uses colors with hue value of 0-40 more frequently. Hue value of roof is concentrated on 0-20, and there is no obvious distinction in different areas. Hue value of wall is concentrated on 0-40, central and south of china uses color with hue value of 21-40 more frequently. Hue value of sign is distributed differently in different area. Central of China uses color with hue value of 21-60 more frequently, west of China uses color with hue value of 0-20 more frequently, north

of China uses color with various hue values.

Saturation value of floor is concentrated on 0-20, but central of China uses colors with saturation values of 41-60, and south of China uses colors with saturation values of 61-80. Saturation value of roof and wall are concentrated on 0-20 in every area. Saturation value of sign has obvious distinction in different area. East, north and west areas are concentrated on 0-20, south and central area are concentrated on 21-40 or 81-100.

Brightness value of floor is concentrated on 81-100 in east, north and west areas, and concentrated on 61-80 in south and central areas. Brightness value of roof is concentrated on 81-100 in every area. Brightness value of wall is concentrated on 81-100 in east, north and west areas, and concentrated on 61-80 in south and central areas. Saturation value of sign has obvious distinction in different areas. Central area are concentrated on 81-100, east and north areas are concentrated on 81-100 or 41-60, west area is concentrated on 0-20 or 61-80.

Graph 1. Color distribution in different area (Hue). Hue value is from 0 to 360, sample's hue value was divided into 18 sections, such as section in 0-20, section in 21-40, as some section has no value, they were not shown here in graph. Proportions of each section were calculated.

As the results mentioned above, colors used in commercial space of south and central area are different with other areas. These two areas' commercial space are more colorful, especially in south of China. Color distribution of south and central area is vivid hue, high saturation and high brightness. Color distribution of north, east and west areas is warm hue, lower saturation and lower brightness.

3.2 COLOR DISTRIBUTION IN DIFFERENT TYPE OF COMMERCIAL SPACE

Color distribution in different type of commercial space is shown in graph 3. There are three types of commercial space, department store where is designed for Chinese consumers with high consumption, shopping mall where is designed for consumers with general consumptions or recreational consumptions, and market or supermarket where is designed for consumers with general or lower consumptions.

Hue value of floor is concentrated on 0-20 in all kinds of commercial space, but in market, lots of values are concentrated on 41-60. Hue value of wall is concentrated on 0-20 in market and shopping mall, and concentrated on 21-40 in department store. Hue value of sign in market is concentrated on 0-20, but

the value of sign in department store and shopping mall is dispersed in lots of hue values. Saturation value of floor, roof and wall are all concentrated on 0-20 in all kinds of commercial space. Saturation value of sign has obvious distinction in different type of space. In supermarket, saturation value is concentrated on 81-100 or 0-20, in department store, saturation value is concentrated on 21-40, in shopping store, saturation value is concentrated on 0-20. Brightness value of floor in supermarket is concentrated on 61-80, and the value in department store or in shopping mall is concentrated on 81-100. Brightness value of wall and roof are all concentrated on 81-100 in all kinds of space. Brightness value of sign has obvious distinction in different type of space. In supermarket, saturation value is concentrated on 61-100; in department store, saturation value is concentrated on 21-60; in shopping store, saturation value is dispersed from 0 to 100.

As the results mentioned above, although interior colors used in three kinds of commercial space have no great difference, the brightness in supermarket is darker than other spaces, and the sign colors used in these space are quiet different with each other.

Graph 2. Color distribution in different area (Saturation & Brightness). Hue value is from 0 to 360, sample's hue value was divided into 18 sections, such as section in 0-20, section in 21-40, as some section has no value, they were not shown here in graph. Proportions of each section were calculated. ◆ east ▲ south ■ central * north × west

department are brighter than others, supermarket are darker than others.

4. CONCLUSION

4.1 COLOR SCHEME OF DIFFERENT AREAS

Results shows that color scheme in commercial space have distinction in different areas in China. Color distribution of south and central area is vivid hue, high saturation and high brightness. Color distribution of north, east and west areas is warm hue, lower saturation and lower brightness.

As the color scheme in south and central China, the hue value is consentrated on 20-100, the saturation value is 0-20, the brightness value is 61-80.

As the color scheme in north, west and east China, the hue value is consentrated on 0-40, the saturation value is 0-20, the brightness value is 81-

100.

4.2 COLOR SCHEME IN DIFFERENT TYPE OF COMMERCIAL SPACE

Results shows that color scheme in commercial space have distinction in different type of commercial space. The brightness in supermarket is darker than other spaces, and the sign colors used in these space are quiet different with each other. Department are brighter than others, supermarket are darker than others.

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Graph 3. Color distribution in different type of commercial space (Hue, Saturation & Brightness). Hue value is from 0 to 360, sample's hue value was divided into 18 sections, such as section in 0-20, section in 21-40, as some section has no value, they were not shown here in graph. Proportions of each section were calculated. ◆ department store ▲ shopping mall ■ supermarket

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